

Street Vending in Sikkim: Gendered Inequalities and Urban Informal Livelihood in Northeast India

Mandeep Dhamala and Ruma Kundu

Street vending is an integral part of the urban informal economy in Northeast India. It has been a source of livelihood for marginalised people in urban and semi-urban areas. This paper explores the socioeconomic status of street vendors in eight major towns in Sikkim, focusing on their income disparities, vulnerabilities and the role of gender. A total sample size of 310 street vendors was selected from eight major towns in the state. A stratified purposive sampling method was used and the results were analysed with the help of descriptive statistics such as frequency and percentages. Factors influencing the income of vendors were analysed through a multiple linear regression model. Findings show that the majority of the vendors have minimal educational attainments. Though most of them reside in pucca houses and have access to basic amenities like water, electricity and sanitation, they still face precarious economic conditions. Education emerges as a significant predictor of income, while loss in vending days due to illness, social obligations and eviction negatively impacts earnings. Further analysis reveals that women vendors earn less in almost all towns because they work few hours and face greater domestic and caregiving burdens. These inequalities are more severe among SC and ST women with minimal education. These findings highlight the intersectional nature of exclusion in urban informal spaces. This requires more inclusive urban policy such as gender-sensitive interventions, targeted support for marginalised groups and improved policy implementation that will transform street vending as a source of sustainable livelihood rather than a survival strategy.

Keywords: Street Vending, Socioeconomic Aspects, Income Disparity, Marginalisation, Sikkim

Introduction

Street vending has been a fundamental mode of selling goods and services in human communities since ancient times, predating the establishment of formal markets. In urban areas, vendors can be seen either moving along streets or operating from fixed points alongside thoroughfares. Over time, formal markets may develop at these locations, initially starting as weekly markets or haats and eventually evolving into daily commercial markets. Even in modern developing economies, street vending remains

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a prevalent method of buying and selling goods (Bhowmik, 2007). Street vendors play a crucial role in urban environments by providing an informal market for pedestrians and residents, expanding the reach of goods and services. According to the National Policy on Urban Street Vendors (2004), a street vendor is defined as a seller offering goods for public sale without a permanent built-up structure. Stationary vendors typically occupy street pavements or other public spaces, while mobile vendors or hawkers sell their goods at various points along their routes. Street vending in India is a common business activity and it represents a vast and socioeconomically diverse population. Amrutha & Cholakkal (2021) reveal that street vendors in India come from a low-income background, which is characterised by struggles with irregular income and job security. Their dependence on daily sales from vending makes them more vulnerable to economic fluctuations.

In Sikkim, street vending is an important economic activity that plays a crucial role in the socio-economic dynamics of urban as well as rural areas by providing easy access to residents. Though street vending plays an important role in the informal economy, they are in a marginalised position, struggling to earn a livelihood and support themselves. Additionally, Barman (2020) pointed out that the limited formal education and skillset restricts access to other job opportunities for street vendors. Their marginalisation is made worse by the constant threat of eviction caused by the absence of vending zones, as well as exploitation by the middlemen. Despite all these challenges street vending in Sikkim has remained the easiest informal activity concerning location, and type of goods sold, significantly influencing a vendor's income and overall socioeconomic standing.

Street vending is significant in Sikkim due to the diverse backgrounds of the vendors in the market and their ability to meet a variety of consumer needs. Street vendors play a crucial role in both urban and rural parts of the state, whether in the capital city Gangtok or in the isolated market of Mangan. Street vendors offer necessary items to consumers on a daily basis.

Nevertheless, there is still a lack of exploration in the socioeconomic study of street vendors in Sikkim, with very few empirical studies examining demographic characteristics, earnings and market trends. This research aims to address this gap by carrying out a thorough examination of street vending using primary data gathered from eight main towns in the state.

The study will also help to understand the challenges faced by street vendors and highlight new opportunities in the informal market of Sikkim. Altogether the study will help to frame an inclusive policy for the betterment of street vendors and sustainable urban development.

This paper investigates the socioeconomic status, livelihood dynamics and the gendered dynamics among the street vendors across eight town in Sikkim.

The objectives of the present effort are as follow:

1. Evaluate the socio-economic characteristics and livelihood strategies of street vendors across various towns in Sikkim.
2. Investigate the factors influencing the profitability and economic performance of street vending businesses in different urban areas of Sikkim.

3. To understand gender-based disparities among street vendors in Sikkim.

To understand and answer these research questions, primary data has been collected from 310 street vendors using stratified purposive sampling strategy. The data has been analysed using descriptive and regression analysis to examine the role of gender, working hours, education and household characteristics in shaping vendors' income and sustainability of livelihoods.

Our findings shows that street vending activity is mainly dominated by women constituting more than 60% in the most vulnerable areas of the unorganised sector. Also, regression analysis highlights that female vendors earn substantially less compared to male counterparts mainly due to their care responsibilities and limited daily work hours. Furthermore, the majority of the vendors belong to marginalised social groups (Schedule Tribes, Schedule Castes, and OBCs) and live in semi-permanent dwellings with varying access to basic amenities. Education is found to be a key predictor of income, yet a large proportion of vendors lack formal education. These findings highlights the complex relationship of opportunities and vulnerabilities in street vending activities. Though it offers income and opportunities, yet social and gendered exclusion persists.

This paper contributes to the literature on the informal economy by highlighting the gendered aspect of informality offering fresh insight from a less studied region viz., Sikkim. Further, it also compliments the literature on urban street vending by bringing a feminist and intersectional perspective in the discussion. It also contributes to policy discussion on inclusive urban planning, social provisioning in state which was the central theme of the Street Vendors Act of 2014.

Literature Review

Street vending plays an important role in providing employment and livelihood to millions of urban poor across the Global South. Defined as a person selling goods and services in public spaces without any permanent or fixed stall (Bhowmik, 2005), it plays a vital role in sustaining urban economies (Roever & Skinner, 2016). They are critical in providing employment and livelihood in countries like Thailand, South Africa, Brazil and Bangkok (Roever, 2014; Skinner, 2008). The presence of street vendors in the urban market creates ease for the urban population by providing affordable goods and services to underserved populations. However, they face numerous challenges such as harassment from authorities, confiscation of goods, lack of property rights and subsistence living (Wongtada, 2014; ILO, 2018). These challenges in their daily activities, such as legal obstacles, lack of access to resources, and the impact of technological changes, exacerbate their socioeconomic conditions. Despite the positive impact of street vending in urban spaces it has been historically under-recognised in India. The Street Vendors (Protection of Livelihood and Regulation of Street Vending) Act, 2014, is a landmark policy aimed at protecting the rights of vendors, but despite these efforts, studies indicate persistent challenges remain on the implementation of the act, conflict over urban spaces and others (Kumari, 2015). This Act represents a crucial step towards recognising street vendors in the urban informal economy. However, effective implementation of the policy is essential for addressing the problems

vendors face; gender-specific impacts and outcome must be examined. Furthermore, the actual implementation of this policy remains inconsistent, particularly in geographically isolated regions like Northeast India.

In recent times street vending has garnered increased attention due to its significant role in addressing various forms of inequality (Peimani & Kamalipour, 2022). Research from the Global South including Sub-Saharan Africa, and Latin America consistently shows that women in the informal economy have to operate under precarious conditions (Hammer & Ness, 2021). For instance Chan (2021) highlights that women street vendors are often confined to lower- income with limited sanitation and security in their workplace.

Recent studies highlight the complex gender dynamics of street vending in India. Anjaria, (2006) pointed out that gender and caste are important in accessing resources and opportunities for vendors in India. Research on gender disparity highlights significant challenges faced by female vendors. Safety concerns and wage disparities persist throughout. Factors such as household responsibilities, limited access to capital, and selling less profitable goods contribute to less earnings by female vendors (Murangwa & Njaya, 2016). Other factors like location play a crucial role in determining female vendors' income (Wang et al., 2024). A study by Sharma (2024) highlights that patriarchal norms and societal expectations in some areas limit women's education and formal employment, often leaving street vending as the only viable livelihood option. As this study reveals, in Sikkim, women vendors significantly outnumber male counterparts, highlighting the importance of this sector; however they earn significantly less than men. This calls for a feminist political economy lens that views gender not merely as a demographic variable but as a structural axis of exclusion.

Street vendors have to work long hours to meet their basic needs, and they have low and irregular incomes. Most of the street vendors in India earn below minimum wage, making it difficult to achieve financial stability (Sharma et al., 2006). Street vendors are mainly excluded from the formal financing system, and often, they self-finance their business or rely on informal credit sources, exacerbating their vulnerability (Jamir & Pongen, 2022). Lack of employment opportunities in rural areas, uncertainty in formal sectors and migration are some of the reasons for an increase in the number of street vendors across urban centres (Roeksiripat, 2016). Most of these vendors possess minimal educational attainments, limiting their upward mobility; higher income and investment are observed among educated vendors (Jamir & Pongen, 2022). However, it has also been observed that over some time, vendors will be equipped with knowledge of negotiating and managing inventory, compensating for formal training (Bhowmik, 2005).

In recent times, the socioeconomic status of street vendors has garnered significant importance in research. However, street vendors face numerous challenges in their daily activities, such as legal obstacles, lack of access to resources, and the impact of technological changes, which exacerbate their socioeconomic conditions. Street vendors are characterised by low income, easy entry, and self-employment, which play a vital role in the urban economy, and they mainly come from poor and uneducated backgrounds in rural areas (Iman, 2021). Despite their significant contribution to the

informal economy, to employment generation and easy access to affordable goods, they receive little attention from policymakers. Their financial instability was further exacerbated due to their informality and working conditions without legal protection (Rover & Skinner, 2016). In India, limited access to finance and insurance remains a significant challenge, which compounds their vulnerability. Vasudeva et al. (2024) conducted a study in Chandigarh, revealing that family income and education have a positive impact on insurance coverage; but still, the percentage of enrolment remained low. This gap makes vendors more susceptible to economic shocks because most of them operate without safety nets.

Within northeast India, scholars like Gogoi & Bhattacharyya (2022) have investigated urban informality in Assam, suggesting spatial marginalisation and significant lack of policy reach. Similar trends has been observed in other north-eastern states like Nagaland and Manipur (S & Riongchang, 2023; Devi & Sachdeva, 2022), where street vending remains an important source of income but is under regulated. Informal activity is dominant in major towns of the northeast states, and street vending plays an important role in urban centres such as Imphal, Guwahati and Gangtok. Limited industrialisation in this region shrinks formal employment opportunities. Thus, the informal sector plays an important role in employing marginalised communities, including women. Street vendors in these regions are engaged in selling diverse region-specific goods such as local handicrafts, food items and organic vegetables. . In Sikkim, vendors are engaged in selling organic vegetables and souvenirs, particularly in the city of Gangtok.

While there is extensive research literature on street vending in Indian states, there is a dearth of literature related to Sikkim. This paper fills a significant empirical and analytical gap. First, it offers gender disaggregated insights from a geographically isolated region in national studies on informality. Secondly, it foregrounds intersectionality providing information on how gender, education and caste jointly impact the outcomes in street vending. Finally, it provides an overview of the current scenario of street vending in Sikkim connecting it with the policy landscape, ultimately helping policymakers to assess the sustainability of informal livelihoods and address the limitation of current policy structures. To analyse the dynamics of street vending in Sikkim, this study draws on an intersectional feminist political economy framework. Intersectionality, originally theorised in her seminal paper by Crenshaw (1989), later extended by scholars such as Collins (2022) and Rege (1998), offers a strong lens of understanding on the experiences of the people who suffered oppression. Originally the paper was intended to highlight the struggles of black women in the United States (US) legal system. Since then intersectionality has been adopted and adapted globally, to unpack how gender, caste, class, religion and ethnicity interact to shape the outcomes.

In the context of street vending in the informal economy, intersectionality demonstrates how gendered experiences are not homogenous. A female vendor's economic reality is determined by her caste, educational background, community affiliation and family background rather than solely by her gender identity. For example, a Schedule Tribe (ST) women vendor with minimal educational qualification working

in a remote town in the northeast substantially differs from upper caste women vending in a metropolis with access to social capital and infrastructure. Thus, this framework helps to uncover gender inequalities which are compounded by limited educational access, caste-based exclusion and spatial marginalisation.

Additionally, this paper also draws on feminist urban theory which examines how patriarchal norms have historically influenced urban planning and economic policy. Scholars such as Kabeer (2016) and McDowell (1991) argue that public spaces and institutions are structured by assumptions about male mobility, productivity and visibility rather than being neutral. This results in women in the informal workforce facing spatial exclusion, infrastructural inadequacies and safety risks such as toilets and well lighted vending zones. By integrating these theoretical perspectives this paper provides an understanding of street vending in Sikkim highlighting gender as well as overall socioeconomic dimensions.

Methodology

To analyse the socioeconomic condition of street vendors involved in selling different items in urban spaces of Sikkim, data were collected through personal interview methods based on pre-structured questionnaires from eight major towns in six districts. The study employed a stratified purposive sampling technique to select street vendors from various regions of Sikkim. Geographical regions (East, South, West, and North) served as strata, with specific towns (Gangtok, Singtam, Pakyong, Namchi, Jorethang, Geyzing, Soreng, and Mangan) being purposively chosen within each region based on their known street vending activities. A total sample size of 310 street vendors was distributed across the regions according to the availability of vendors in the market. The collected data was analysed using appropriate statistical techniques. Descriptive statistics such as frequencies and percentages were computed to summarise the sample characteristics. Table 1 highlights the surveyed market areas from each district; figures in parenthesis represent the sample size from a particular town.

Table 1. Region-wise sample size of street vendors

Region	Study Area	Sample Size
East	Gangtok (60), Singtam (30), Pakyong (30)	120
South	Namchi (60), Jorethang (60)	120
West	Geyzing (30), Soreng (30)	60
North	Mangan (10)	10
Sikkim		310

Note: Figure in parenthesis represents the sample size.

In order to understand the impact of socioeconomic variables on the income of vendors the multiple regression model was utilised, which is specified as:

$$I_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1(\text{age})_i + \beta_2(\text{gen})_i + \beta_3(\text{edu})_i + \beta_4(\text{e_mem})_i + \beta_5(\text{loss})_i + \beta_6(\text{hrs})_i + \varepsilon_i$$

Where I_i indicates monthly income from vending, age is the current age of the

respondents, gen indicates the gender of the respondents, edu represents the education level of the respondents, e_mem indicates total earning members in a household, hrs represents daily shop hours of the vendors, and lastly, loss indicates loss in vending days in a month due to different reasons like eviction, illness, social function and others.

Results and Discussion

Overview of Socio-economic Characteristics of Street Vendors

The demographic profile of street vendors in eight towns of Sikkim, namely Gangtok, Singtam, Pakyong, Namchi, Jorethang, Geyzing, Soreng, and Mangan, provides valuable insights into the composition of this informal sector. Table 2 presents a detailed breakdown of the demographic characteristics, including gender, age, category, religion, and family size, among street vendors in each town.

Demographic Profile

Gender

Street vending is a readily accessible venture in the informal economy, where individuals of all genders to partake. Across towns, both men and women engage in this activity, yet it is noteworthy that female street vendors surpass their male counterparts in numbers. This trend is particularly evident in places like Pakyong, where women constitute 83.33% of street vendors, also Jorethang and Geyzing, where they make up 66.67% each. Throughout Sikkim as a whole, women represent 62.26% of street vendors. This phenomenon underscores the vital role women play in Sikkim's informal economy. The predominance of female street vendors can be attributed to various factors, including their contribution to household income, especially in situations where their spouses or other family members have limited earnings.

Age Structure

Age is considered an important determinant of working capability in informal activities, according to Ilyas et al. (2020). While considering the age distribution of the street vendors across the eight towns in Sikkim, it can be seen that the majority fall within the ages of 31-40 and 41-50 years. In Gangtok and Pakyong 36.66% of vendors belong to the age group of 31-40 years. Similarly in Singtam, 40.00% and 25.00% of vendors in Jorethang are aged 41-50 years.

Data also highlights the significant presence of vendors aged above 50 years which indicates the importance of street vending as a source of livelihood in the state. This finding also highlights that a high number of middle-aged individuals in the state engaged in street vending where the aged is commonly considered as productive age. The presence of a large section of the middle-aged population in street vending activities also suggests limited formal employment opportunities in the state. Additionally, the age range of 31-50 years often coincides with a stage in life where individuals may face various financial obligations, such as supporting their families or meeting educational expenses for their children.

Social Category

Examining the distribution of social categories among street vendors unveils a diverse socio-economic panorama within the informal sector. The largest portion of street vendors in Sikkim falls under the Other Backward Class (OBC) category across all towns, comprising 33.5%, closely trailed by the Scheduled Tribe (ST) population, which ranges at 32.90%. General and Scheduled Caste (SC) categories account for 17.42% and 16.13%, respectively. This distribution underscores the inclusivity of various communities in the street vending occupation, drawing a diverse population from relatively privileged to backward communities.

Religion

Dik et al. (2024) have referred to religion and spirituality as an integral aspect of human life that can have a huge impact on shaping one's life. Analysing the religious composition among street vendors across the eight towns in Sikkim provides insights into the cultural diversity within the informal sector. Hinduism emerges as the predominant religion among street vendors in all towns, with percentages ranging from 60.00% to 80.00%. The presence of small proportions of Christian, Muslim and Buddhist street vendors highlights the religious diversity within Sikkim's informal economy. Christian vendors constitute a notable proportion in some towns, such as Singtam and Jorethang, reflecting the influence of Christianity in certain communities. Similarly, Buddhist vendors are prominent in towns like Namchi and Geyzing, reflecting the Buddhist heritage and population in these areas.

Family Size

Household size is considered an important socioeconomic indicator because it affects both household income and spending. Khan (2009), also found that the larger family size affects the ability of a woman to contribute financially. Data from Table 2 shows that the majority of street vendors have households consisting of 1-4 members throughout the towns. Singtam with 80.00% stands out with a higher proportion of vendors having family sizes of 1-4 members, while Gangtok (50%) has a relatively larger percentage of vendors with 5-8 family members. The distribution of family sizes among street vendors may reflect socio-economic factors such as household income levels, living arrangements, and family duties. Vendors with smaller family sizes may find it easier to balance work and family chores, while vendors with high family members also find the advantage of helping hand in business though they face additional challenges related to caregiving and financial limitations.

Table 2. Demographic profile of street vendors.

Particulars	Gangtok		Singtam		Pakyong		Namchi		Jorethang		Geyzing		Soreng		Mangan		
	Number	Percent	Number	Percent	Number	Percent	Number	Percent	Number	Percent	Number	Percent	Number	Percent	Number	Percent	
Gender																	
Male	27	45.00	13	43.33	5	16.67	25	41.67	20	33.33	10	33.33	13	43.33	4	40.00	
Female	33	55.00	17	56.67	25	83.33	35	58.33	40	66.67	20	66.67	17	56.67	6	60.00	
Age																	
21-30	7	11.66	4	13.33	3	10.00	8	15.00	14	23.33	2	6.67	4	13.33	1	10.00	
31-40	22	36.66	9	30.00	11	36.66	13	21.66	10	16.66	5	16.66	5	16.67	2	20.00	
41-50	15	25.00	12	40.00	7	23.33	14	23.33	15	25.00	6	20.00	7	23.33	2	20.00	
51-60	11	18.36	5	16.66	9	30.00	20	33.33	18	30.00	13	43.33	8	26.66	4	40.00	
61-Ab.	5	8.33	0	00.00	0	00.00	4	6.66	3	5.00	4	13.33	6	20.00	1	10.00	
Category																	
Gen	15	25.00	8	26.67	2	6.67	10	16.67	9	15.00	5	16.67	5	16.67	0	00.00	
SC	10	16.67	6	20.00	2	6.67	9	15.00	14	23.33	4	13.33	5	16.67	0	00.00	
ST	13	21.67	10	33.33	19	63.33	15	25.00	13	21.67	12	40.00	12	40.00	8	80.00	
OBC	22	36.67	6	20.00	7	23.33	26	43.33	24	40.00	9	30.00	8	26.67	2	20.00	
Religion																	
Hindu	40	66.66	22	73.33	22	73.33	48	80.00	45	75.00	22	73.33	18	60.00	3	30.00	
Christian	6	10.00	3	10.00	4	13.33	2	3.33	10	16.67	5	16.67	3	10.00	1	10.00	
Buddhist	6	10.00	2	6.67	4	13.33	8	13.33	3	5.00	3	10.00	6	20.00	6	60.00	
Muslim	8	13.33	3	10.00	0	00.00	2	3.33	2	3.33	0	00.00	3	10.00	0	00.00	
Family Size																	
1-4	27	45.00	24	80.00	20	66.66	45	75.00	31	51.66	17	56.66	22	73.33	8	80.00	
5-8	30	50.00	6	20.00	10	33.33	15	25.00	28	46.66	13	43.33	8	26.66	2	20.00	
9-12	3	5.00	0	00.00	0	00.00	0	00.00	1	1.66	0	00.00	0	00.00	0	00.00	

Source: Primary data

Access to Basic household amenities.

The relationship between household amenities and socioeconomic status will always be positive as higher socioeconomic status leads to more amenities. Studies like Rolfe et al. (2020) reveal that limited access to amenities can worsen health outcomes for those with lower socioeconomic status. The information provided in Table 3 shows an interesting relationship between the types of houses street vendors and ownership status across surveyed towns. Over half (55.16%) of the total respondents live in semi-pucca houses, which are less durable than pucca houses. Notably, these semi-pucca houses are primarily owned by vendors themselves. Among the eight towns, Gangtok has a higher percentage of vendors residing in pucca houses. In the remaining towns, semi-pucca houses are predominant, with the presence of some kutchha houses also. In Pakyong, the majority of houses (90.00%) are semi-pucca and where 93.33% are owned by themselves. This suggests that although vendors have achieved house ownership but lack the resources to upgrade to more durable and desirable pucca houses. These findings also show the domination of local vendors in the majority of small towns like Pakyong, Geyzing, Soreng and Mangan. While other larger towns like Gangtok, Namchi, Jorethang and Singtam highlight the presence of migrant vendors.

On the other hand, the more durable pucca houses, which offer better quality and likely comfortable living, appear to be mostly rented. For example, in Gangtok, while over half (55%) of the housing is pucca, a significant portion of these homes are rented rather than owned, as seen with 48.33% of the vendors living in rented accommodations. This trend suggests that although pucca houses are more desirable, they may be financially inaccessible for many vendors, forcing them to rent rather than own.

Similarly, kutchha houses, characterised by their temporary and often less durable construction, make up a small percentage of housing for street vendors across the surveyed towns. This suggests that a small fraction of vendors in this town live in conditions that might lack stability and long-term security. The small percentage of kutchha houses indicates that while most vendors have access to better housing options, there remains a subset who are disproportionately disadvantaged.

Access to essential services such as electricity, fuel sources and water supply is essential for everyday living. According to the data presented in Table 3, it is encouraging to see that electrification is universal across the towns surveyed, with 100% of vendors in each town having access to electricity. Likewise, the primary source of fuel for cooking is LPG, with high usage rates in almost all towns; for example, 98.33% in Gangtok and a complete 100% in Namchi and Pakyong. However, there are areas where firewood remains in use, especially in Mangan where 60% of vendors rely on it possibly because of the town's cold climate and geographic location.

Likewise, most of the towns have 100% access to water ensuring that street vendors and their families have the necessary resources for drinking, cooking, and sanitation. The availability of basic needs in these towns indicates successful infrastructure growth that sustains essential living conditions. In Singtam, access decreases slightly to 93.33%, showing a small gap in the water supply. In general, the high access rates in urban infrastructure development show significant progress in basic amenities, however, the persistent use of firewood in some towns highlights the continued

Table 3. Access to basic amenities

Particulars	Gangtok		Singtam		Pakyong		Namchi		Jorethang		Geyzing		Soreng		Mangan		
	Number	Percent	Number	Percent	Number	Percent	Number	Percent	Number	Percent	Number	Percent	Number	Percent	Number	Percent	
House Type																	
Pucca	33	55.00	13	43.33	2	6.67	26	43.33	20	33.33	1	3.33	7	23.33	1	10.00	
Semi pucca	24	40.00	13	43.33	27	90.00	27	45.00	30	50.00	26	86.67	17	56.67	7	70.00	
Kutchra	3	5.00	4	13.33	1	3.33	7	11.67	10	16.67	3	10.00	6	20.00	2	20.00	
Self-owned	31	51.67	20	66.67	28	93.33	39	65.00	45	75.00	29	96.67	28	93.33	10	100	
Rented	29	48.33	10	33.33	2	6.67	21	35.00	15	25.00	1	3.33	2	6.67	0	00.00	
Electricity																	
Electrified	60	100	30	100	30	100	60	100	60	100	30	100	30	100	10	100	
Non-electrified	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00	
Fuel sources																	
LPG	59	98.33	29	96.67	30	100	60	100	59	98.33	21	70.00	28	93.33	4	40.00	
Firewood	1	1.67	1	3.33	0	0.00	0	0.00	1	1.67	9	30.00	2	6.67	6	60.00	
Water Supply																	
Yes	60	100	28	93.33	30	100	60	100	60	100	30	100	30	100	10	100	
No	0	0.00	2	6.67	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	00.00	
Household white-goods																	
Smartphone																	
Yes	51	85.00	26	86.67	28	93.33	52	86.67	52	86.67	20	66.67	23	76.67	9	90.00	
No	9	15.00	4	13.33	2	6.67	8	13.33	8	13.33	10	33.33	7	23.33	1	10.00	
Television																	
Yes	40	66.67	19	63.33	22	73.33	31	51.67	37	61.67	15	50.00	15	50.00	3	30.00	
No	20	33.33	11	36.67	8	26.67	29	48.33	23	38.33	15	50.00	15	50.00	7	70.00	
Motorised vehicle																	
Yes	4	6.67	6	20.00	2	6.67	12	20.00	9	15.00	3	10.00	10	33.33	2	20.00	
No	56	93.33	24	80.00	28	93.33	48	80.00	51	85.00	27	90.00	20	66.66	8	80.00	
Refrigerator																	
Yes	40	66.67	17	56.67	18	60.00	23	38.33	35	58.33	15	50.00	11	36.67	0	00.00	
No	20	33.33	13	43.33	12	40.00	37	61.67	25	41.67	15	50.00	19	63.33	10	100	

Source: Primary data

challenges in completely sustainable living conditions for all street vendors.

Furthermore, access to household white goods among street vendors varies significantly across the surveyed towns, indicating disparities in living standards and possibly economic opportunities. These household white goods, which include smartphones, televisions, motorised vehicles, and refrigerators, are important for connectivity, information access, and overall quality of life. Most of the street vendors in towns have smartphones, with a high percentage across all towns. For example, 93.33% of the individuals in Pakyong and 86.67% in Namchi possess smartphones. Access to television is somewhat lower but still significant, indicating that many vendors have a basic level of digital entertainment and information. In Jorethang, 61.67% of vendors own a television. The lowest access is in Mangan, where only 30% have televisions, possibly reflecting economic limitations or choices in spending priorities. Refrigerator ownership also shows significant variation. In Gangtok, 66.67% of vendors own a refrigerator, while in Mangan, no vendors reported owning one which is obvious due to its cold weather conditions. This appliance is crucial for food storage and safety, and its varied ownership may indicate disparities in income levels or access to purchasing power.

Socio-economic status

Marital status

Table 4 illustrates the marital status of the street vendors in Sikkim where the majority (87.42%) of total vendors are married. This highlights the predominance of married individuals with the lowest marital percentage of 76.67% in Soreng to 100% in Mangan. Married street vendors also have an advantage and benefit from shared responsibilities and resources within their households, which could contribute to their ability to sustain their vending businesses. A large number of married and women getting involved in street vending can also be attributed to earning a supplementary source of income. Generally, women take street vending to earn supplementary income to support their main income. The proportion of single-street vendors is relatively low across all towns. Likewise, the proportion of separated and widowed vendors are present in small numbers in some towns and their presence demonstrates the resilience and adaptability of individuals who face challenges but continue to engage in economic activities to support themselves and their families.

Literacy and Education

Education plays an important role in any activity and Table 4 provides valuable information about the educational background of individuals involved in street vending activities in Sikkim. 39.35% of the total population has completed high school (6-12 years), ranging from 53.33% in Pakyong to 30.00% in Geyzing. This indicates that the majority of street vendors have finished high school which may help them in dealing with more challenging responsibilities, communicating with customers, and understanding the rules and regulations associated with street vending.

Furthermore, a substantial percentage of street vendors have completed primary education (1-5 years), with proportions varying from 36.66% in Gangtok to 23.33% in

Soreng. This indicates that many street vendors in Sikkim have acquired primary education, which has developed fundamental reading and math abilities, which can help them in daily business activities.

In addition, only street vendors (4.83%) have graduate and above qualifications across all towns. Though this percentage is relatively low, their presence highlights qualified individuals who can also join the street trade. The presence of individuals with higher educational attainments also brings specialized skills, knowledge, and perspectives to their businesses which can boost their income.

Nevertheless, it is worth mentioning that 22.90% of the total street vendors have reported no formal education, ranging from 13.33% in Pakyong to 36.67% in Soreng. This highlights the challenges faced by individuals with limited education, as they may struggle to other ways of making a livelihood outside street vending or may find it difficult to find formal jobs.

Earning and Dependent Members

The majority of street vendors have one or two people in their households who contribute to earnings. This shows that many vendors depend on income from street vending as their main income. This implies that street vending is important for helping individuals and families earn income, which helps to maintain financial stability and overall well-being. Similarly, the distribution of dependent members among street vendors reveals varying household sizes and additional responsibilities. A considerable proportion of street vendors have between zero to two dependent members in their households, indicating relatively smaller family sizes or fewer dependents requiring financial support. However, a notable portion of vendors also have three to five dependent members, indicating bigger family sizes or additional caregiving duties that may impact household finances and livelihood approaches.

Vending Experience

The distribution of vending experience among street vendors reflects a range of skill levels and tenure within the informal economy. On average, street vendors in eight towns have vending experience of 14.17 years. Approximately 30% to 60% of vendors in every town have been vending for 1-10 years. This implies that new individuals joining street vending or a continuous influx of individuals join it. The distribution also reveals a diverse range of experiences, with some vendors having between 11 to 20 years or even 21 to 30 years of vending experience. This highlights the presence of experienced vendors who have kept their business running for a long period. Experienced vendors understand market demand and also have connections and a customer base that generally positively correlates with income. Additionally, a smaller proportion of vendors have reported over 30 years of vending experience. The presence of experienced vendors also implies that street vending has provided a stable source of income for many for a long time which shows the importance of the informal economy in the state.

Monthly Vending Profit

The analysis of monthly vending profit among street vendors in Sikkim reveals

variations across different towns, with some towns experiencing higher profitability levels than others. 49.03% of the total vendors earn a profit between 10,001 to 15,000 rupees per month, whereas Gangtok stands out with 75.00% of vendors earning profits between 10,001 to 15,000 rupees per month, suggesting comparatively strong market demand in the capital city. This could be attributed to factors such as higher footfall, tourism, and also higher percentage of the population, which contribute to increased sales and profitability for street vendors in Gangtok. On the other hand, vendors from smaller towns earn lower profits ranging from 0 to 5,000 rupees per month. This disparity in profitability could be attributed to various factors such as limited market demand, lower purchasing power among local residents, or challenges related to infrastructure and accessibility. For example, Pakyong and Mangan being a relatively smaller town, may have fewer economic opportunities and lower population density compared to larger urban centres like Gangtok and Namchi resulting in reduced sales and profitability for street vendors operating in the area.

Gendered Dimensions of Street Vending in Sikkim

Street vending serves as a source of livelihood for many in urban spaces of Sikkim. Women vendors constitute the numerical majority across towns but their experiences differ from the male counterparts. Many of the women vendors faces challenges such as lower income, more caregiving responsibilities and fewer working hours. This section highlights gender-disaggregated analysis along with patterns of income, education and time spent on vending between male and female vendors, thereby further highlighting difficulties faced by women and unequal opportunities within the informal economy.

Table 5: Gendered Vendors Composition by Town

Towns	Female (%)	Male (%)
Namchi	35 (58.33)	25(41.67)
Jorethang	40 (66.67)	20(33.33)
Gangtok	33 (55.00)	27(45.00)
Geyzing	20 (66.67)	10(33.33)
Soreng	17 (56.67)	13 (43.33)
Pakyong	25 (83.33)	5 (16.67)
Singtam	17 (56.67)	13(43.33)
Mangan	6 (60.00)	4(40.00)
All Vendors	193 (62.26)	117 (37.73)

Source: Primary Survey

Table 5 above clearly highlights that female vendors outnumber male vendors across eight towns indicating the role of women in the urban informal economy in providing livelihood. This widespread presence also suggests that street vending is not supplementary source of income but primary source of livelihood. However, in the subsequent tables and figures it shows that this visibility does not translate into equality in working conditions, income or education.

Table 4. Socio-economic status of street vendors

Particulars	Gangtok		Singtam		Pakyong		Nanchi		Jorethang		Geyzing		Soreng		Mangan	
	Number	Percent	Number	Percent	Number	Percent	Number	Percent	Number	Percent	Number	Percent	Number	Percent	Number	Percent
Marital Status																
Single	2	3.33	1	3.33	0	0.00	5	8.33	6	10.00	2	6.67	4	13.33	0	00.00
Married	54	90.00	29	96.67	29	96.67	50	83.33	51	85.00	25	83.33	23	76.67	10	100
Widow	3	5.00	0	0.00	1	3.33	5	8.33	3	5.00	3	10.00	3	10.00	0	00.00
Separated	1	1.67	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	00.00	0	00.00	0	00.00	0	00.00
Education																
No Formal Education	17	28.33	5	16.67	4	13.33	9	15.00	13	21.67	10	33.33	11	36.67	2	20.00
Primary (1-5)	22	36.66	10	33.33	9	30.00	20	33.33	21	35.00	9	30.00	7	23.33	4	40.00
Highschool (6-12)	19	31.66	14	46.66	16	53.33	27	45.00	22	36.66	9	30.00	11	36.67	4	40.00
Graduate & ab.	2	3.33	1	3.33	1	3.33	4	6.66	4	6.67	2	6.67	1	3.33	0	00.00
Vending Experience (in years)																
01-10	31	51.66	13	43.33	18	60.00	29	48.33	29	48.33	9	30.00	13	43.33	3	30.00
11-20	16	26.66	11	36.66	6	20.00	21	35.00	21	35.00	10	33.33	8	26.66	5	50.00
21-30	9	15.00	5	16.66	6	20.00	8	13.33	10	16.66	10	33.33	7	23.33	1	10.00
31 & Ab	4	6.66	1	3.33	0	0.00	2	3.33	0	00.00	1	3.33	2	6.66	1	10.00
Earning Members																
1	17	28.33	12	40.00	7	23.33	26	43.33	26	43.33	15	50.00	17	56.67	5	50.00
2	40	66.67	16	53.33	22	73.33	30	50.00	27	45.00	13	43.33	11	36.67	3	30.00
3 & Ab.	3	5.00	2	6.67	1	3.33	4	6.67	7	11.67	2	6.67	2	6.67	2	20.00
Dependent Members																
0-2	20	33.33	24	80.00	17	56.66	41	68.33	32	53.33	13	43.33	16	53.33	5	50.00
3-5	35	58.33	5	16.66	12	40.00	18	30.00	27	45.00	17	56.66	13	43.33	5	50.00
6 & Ab.	5	8.33	1	3.33	1	3.33	1	1.67	1	1.67	0	00.00	1	3.33	0	00.00
Monthly Vending Profit																
0-5000	2	3.33	0	0.00	1	3.33	1	1.67	9	15.00	1	3.33	1	3.33	3	30.00
5001-10000	45	75.00	6	20.00	18	60.00	19	31.66	29	48.33	10	33.33	16	53.33	6	60.00
10001-15000	11	18.33	17	56.66	9	30.00	21	35.00	12	20.00	12	40.00	9	30.00	1	10.00
15001-20000	2	3.33	6	20.00	2	6.67	10	16.66	4	6.66	6	20.00	3	10.00	0	00.00
20001-25000	0	00.00	1	3.33	0	0.00	6	10.00	4	6.66	0	00.00	1	3.33	0	00.00
25000 and Ab.	0	00.00	0	00.00	0	00.00	3	5.00	2	3.33	1	3.33	0	00.00	0	00.00

Source: Primary Survey

Figure 1 illustrates the average monthly income of male and female vendors across surveyed towns in Sikkim. In every town, male vendors consistently earn more than female vendors. This gender gap is wider in towns like Geyzing and Singtam despite the high proportion of the female vendors with a monthly income difference of 3600 and 2430 rupees respectively. This income gap among the vendors is not a reflection of individual productivity alone but structural effects of the gender disadvantages. Field experiences highlighted that most of the female vendors across towns vend in low-footfall areas, face higher risk of eviction or harassment, and operate with less access to infrastructure and credit. As mentioned by Alfafa et al. (2018), income disparity exists among vendors with location of operation significantly impacting earnings. These overall differences in the earnings highlights the larger problem in the system. Female vendors are often placed in low-footfall areas resulting limited cash flow to up-scale their business.

Figure 1: Monthly Income Disparity by Gender across Towns

Source: Primary Survey

Similarly Figure 2 illustrates the average number of working hours male and female vendors spent in vending each day in different towns. It is evident that across all towns, male vendors work more hours compared to female vendors. It shows that the gender gap in working time is evident and persistent with male vendors working longer often by one to two hours per day. This difference is critical because it directly correlates with their earnings. Women vendors are often forced for the double shift made up of paid street vending and unpaid domestic duties. As highlighted by Sharma (2024), time constraints due to household caregiving responsibilities often reduces their working time directly reflecting on their income. This is also clear from the bar chart; across all towns women vendors report significantly higher caregiving and domestic responsibilities than men. This constrains women’s ability to fully participate in the informal economy with the result that they have to leave work early and decline opportunities to expand. This aligns with global findings that one of the primary

barriers to women’s economic empowerment in the informal sector is gender inequality in care burdens (Esquivel, 2013).

Figure 2: Gendered Constraints on Time and Labour

Source: Primary Survey

Table 6 presents the average monthly income and education levels of the street vendors in Sikkim, broken down by caste and gender. It can be seen from the table that across all social groups men consistently earn more than women. This highlights that gender-based inequality persists in the informal economy across all caste groups. For instance, in OBC category, men earn Rs. 13,507 per month, while women earn Rs. 11,975. The same situation exists in case of the ST category, despite female vendors having higher average education (6.25 years) than male counterparts (5.08 years). These findings show that education alone does not guarantee better earnings for women. Other factors such as access to vending zones, safety, working hours and market discrimination came into play.

The situation is more concerning for SC women, who have the lowest level of education (1.86 years) and the lowest average monthly income (Rs. 9,207). The condition

of SC male vendors is also not good; their average monthly income is just Rs. 10,667 though they nearly have twice the level of schooling compared to females. This highlights how intersecting disadvantages of caste and gender combine to shape economic outcome. Even when women have similar or better education than male counterparts their earnings remain lower; this suggests that gender-based discrimination operates independent of education.

Table 6: Intersectional Income by Social Group & Education Social Group

	Gender	Avg. Monthly Income (Rs.)	Avg. Education (Years)
General	Male	12200	4.83
	Female	10739.13	4.86
OBC	Male	13507.14	5.73
	Female	11975.81	5.48
ST	Male	12434.78	5.08
	Female	10803.8	6.25
SC	Male	10666.67	4.42
	Female	9206.897	1.86

Source: Primary Survey

This table highlights the need of policies that go beyond general support to street vendors, ensuring that policy intervention must be targeted to marginalised sections such as SC, ST and women. These findings align with intersectional feminist theory, which suggests that gender inequality needs to be looked through other lens such as caste and class. It also shows the layered marginalisation, offering both empirical evidence and a call for more inclusive and just urban policy.

Regression Analysis of Factors Influencing Street Vendor Income

Table 7 provides a brief summary of key independent variables which are likely to impact the monthly earnings of street vendors. Table 7 shows that the average age of the vendors is around 45.2 years. It also shows that the vending market in Sikkim is mainly dominated by female vendors (62.2%). The majority of the vendors has completed an average of 5 years of formal education. Data also highlights that on average there are 1.7 earning members in vendor households along with the fact that vendors lose an average of 12.38 days monthly due to different reasons such as eviction, social obligation and illness. Lastly, on an average, vendors mainly operate their shop for 8.6 hours per day.

To understand the impact of independent variables on the monthly income of the street vendors the multiple linear regression model has been used. Table 8 represents the results of a regression analysis examining the factors that influence the monthly income of the street vendors in eight different towns of Sikkim. Among the independent variables except age, all other variables are statistically significant with their expected signs. Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) was calculated for each explanatory variable to evaluate the presence of multicollinearity. The average VIF for the model was 1.67 suggesting moderate multicollinearity which is not generally considered as a major

concern (Shrestha, 2020).

Table 7: Summary of the Variables

Variables	Description	Mean
Age	Age of the respondents	45.57
Gender	Gender of the respondents (Male=0, 1=otherwise)	62.20
Education	Number of years of schooling of the respondents	5.16
Earning members	Total earning members in a household	1.70
Loss in vending days	Loss in vending days in the current month due to reasons like eviction, social function, illness, & others	12.38
Daily shop hours	Daily shop of vendors	8.60

Table 8: Factors Influencing Monthly Income of Street Vendors in Sikkim

Variables	coefficients	t	p-value
<i>Dependent Variable:</i>			
<i>Monthly Income of</i>			
Vendors Intercept	1515.70	0.18	0.854
Age	63.3707	0.56	0.577
Gender	-3251.19	-1.99	0.056*
Education	837.4742	3.13	0.001***
Earning members	8316.5368	7.08	0.000***
Loss in vending days	-294.6349	-1.74	0.082*
Daily shop hours	1420.60	2.63	0.009***
R-square	0.2398		
F-Value	15.93		0.000***
No. of observations	310		
Mean VIF	1.67		

Note: *, ** and *** indicates the significance levels at 10%, 5% and 1% respectively.

From table 8, it is clear that the variables like gender, education, earning members in a household, loss in vending days and daily shop hours of the vendors have a statistically significant impact on the monthly income of the vendors. The result shows that the education level and the loss in vending days of vendors are statistically significant at a 10 per cent level of significance. The negative coefficient of the gender suggests that being female in the street vending business in Sikkim results in a decrease in monthly income compared to their male counterparts. These findings are in line with those of Njaya (2016) who also obtained similar results for income disparity between male and female street vendors. The disparity in income is mainly due to the difference in daily shop hours between male and female vendors as most of the female vendors have to look after unpaid family chores. Similarly, the negative coefficient for loss on vending days implies that approximately a loss of 295 rupees occurs on each vending day.

The results also show that education, earning members and daily shop hours are

statistically significant at a 1 per cent level with positive coefficients. Several studies like Hansmann, Baur, and Binder (2020), Recchi (2020) and Chettri and Kundu (2020) have suggested a positive relationship between education and earnings of informal workers. It is obvious that vendors with better education will tend to have a positive correlation with income mainly due to the development of valuable skills like marketing, financial management, and negotiation tactics which ultimately impacts their earnings. It is clear that education, earning members and daily shop hours are strong predictors of monthly income which is indicated by their respective p-values. These findings highlight that on an average increase in one unit of education, earning members in household and daily shop hours will lead to an increase in the monthly income of vendors by ¹ 838/, ¹ 8317/ and ¹ 1420/ respectively. Amongst the independent variables, only age has no statistically significant impact on the monthly earnings of street vendors in Sikkim.

Since almost all the regressors have a statistically significant impact on the monthly income of the vendors, in spite of the low R-square, it can be easily said that the model is rather a good fit. This is also confirmed by the statistically significant value of the F test statistic.

Conclusion

Street vending plays a vital role in urban economies, but it is frequently underestimated and ignored by government and local authorities. This extensive study carried out on 310 street vendors from eight major towns in Sikkim shows that most of the street vendors are economically disadvantaged, with limited formal education and skills. A small segment of the vendors are highly educated and opt for street vending due to a lack of formal employment opportunities.

The research also shows that street vending often acts as a supplementary source of income, especially for women. It also indicates that a significant number of vendors provide financial support to family members who depend upon them. Experience levels vary, with 30% to 60% of vendors across the towns reporting 1 to 10 years of vending experience. Among the towns, Gangtok stands out for its relatively high vendor earnings of 10,001 to 15,000 rupees per month, likely due to factors such as higher pedestrian traffic, tourist presence, and a diverse customer base that enhances sales opportunities. In contrast, towns like Pakyong and Mangan show a higher number of vendors earning between 0 to 5,000 rupees monthly, indicating less favourable market conditions or a small size of the market.

The regression analysis also shows the factors influencing the income of street vendors in Sikkim. The findings suggest that better education and diligence lead to better income. These results also reveal the interplay between opportunities for sustainable livelihood and vulnerabilities pushing them into marginalisation. Though education offers vendor skills and a path towards a more sustainable livelihood, factors like loss in vending days align with income disparities creating challenges. Importantly, women vendors in some towns still earn less despite having comparable or even higher education mainly due to shorter vending hours, caregiving responsibilities and limited access to appropriate vending locations.

The socioeconomic study of street vendors in Sikkim provides valuable insights

into the informal economy of the state and its role in urban areas. Street vendors are present in every nook of the city and provide easy access to daily commodities at affordable prices, bridging the gap between rural produce and urban demand. However, they faced several challenges, including irregular income and legal recognition. However, these challenges are not the same for all vendors. Women, especially from ST and SC backgrounds face additional disadvantages, even in towns where they are in the majority.

Examining the socioeconomic status of street vendors in Sikkim, several key insights have been unfolded. First, street vending provides a means to livelihood for the urban poor and rural migrants of the state, and also, they provide jobs to other informal workers like potters. Many individuals join street trade out of necessity due to a lack of formal employment. Secondly, vendors in the state are heavily relied on for selling vegetables and other tourist attractions.

In addition to these findings, the study reveals that gender plays an important role and significantly influences who gains and who encounters obstacles from street vending. Despite being in the majority in most of the towns, women earn significantly less than men because of unpaid household duties. These challenges are more acute for women from SC and ST communities who have lower educational attainments. This demonstrates that marginalisation in the informal economy is not experienced equally. Gender, caste and education intersect in complex way to shape disadvantage. This underscores that street vending in Sikkim is not merely a form of livelihood but a key part of urban informal economy that links rural products to urban demands and family survival. Women play a significant role in connecting essential and affordable goods to urban dwellers while managing other responsibilities. More broadly, these patterns reflect common trends across northeast India, where street vending is integral part of the informal economy but remains under-regulated and gendered. This calls for policies to look beyond one-size-fits-all regulations and embrace intersectional, regionally-informed, and gender-sensitive frameworks. While the Street Vendors (Protection of Livelihood and Regulation of Street Vending) Act, 2014 aims to protect marginalised vendors but its implementation in Sikkim remains weak. Vendors from most of the towns are unaware of these rights, leaving them vulnerable to municipal actions.

First, awareness of vending zones must be incorporated into urban planning processes. As mandated by the Act, Town Vending Committee (TVCs), must be formed with an active participation of women and marginalised social groups to ensure equity in the allocation of spaces. Secondly, the current framework is gender-neutral and gender must be explicitly addressed in the design of vending policies. Policies should incorporate provision for flexible licensing hours and safety mechanisms such as proper lighting, toilets and police support which is often overlooked. Thirdly, economic support programmes, such as microcredit, skill development, and health insurance focused on women vendors, specially from marginalised social groups, will help these sections. Lastly, awareness campaigns, financial literacy programmes and legal literacy initiatives to inform vendors about the Act are necessary.

By focusing on these inclusive measures, the state can ensure that street vending becomes a more secure and sustainable livelihood for those who need it the most

rather than just a survival strategy.

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